

Instabilities-Induced Pattern Formations in Soft Composites for Mechanical Metamaterials

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Experimental observation of wavy patterns in laminates

Li, Kaynia, Rudykh, Boyce, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* (2013); Rudykh & Boyce, *PRL* (2014)

Rudykh & Slesarenko, *Soft Matter* (2016)

Onset of Instabilities and Post-bifurcation

Microscopic Instabilities

Bloch-Floquet analysis:
scan finite wave-number $|\mathbf{k}| \neq 0$

Long Wave Instabilities

Loss of Ellipticity Analysis:
 $|\mathbf{k}| \rightarrow 0$ $\mathcal{A}_{\alpha i \beta j}(\mathbf{F}) n_\alpha n_\beta m_i m_j > 0$
tensor of instantaneous elastic moduli

Rudykh & Boyce, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* (2014)

Wrinkling interfaces in soft layered materials

Geometry and phase properties define **only single unique** wavy structure

Rate-dependent materials for **tuning** wavy structure

Strain-Rate Effect: Experiments & Simulations

Slesarenko & Rudykh, *Soft Matter* (2016)

Microscopic instabilities in 3D Fiber composites

Slesarenko & Rudykh, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* (2017)

Critical Wavelengths

3D fiber composites develop **helical** structures

Experiments: Stress vs Strain

Experiments vs Simulations: Critical Wavenumber

Li, Slesarenko, Galich & Rudykh, *Composites B* (2018)

Periodic Fiber Arrangements

Fiber arrangement: Simulations & Experiments

Li, Slesarenko, Galich & Rudykh, *Composites B* (2018)

Fiber arrangement: Simulations & Experiments

Galich, Slesarenko, Li & Rudykh, *Int. J. Eng. Science* (2018)

Soft Composites: Auxetic Behavior and Band Gaps

Undeformed

Deformed

Auxetic behavior

Acoustic metamaterial

Soft Transformable Metamaterials with Hexagonal Networks

Stiffness Ratio

Gao, Slesarenko, Boyce, Rudykh & Li, *Scientific Reports* (2018)

Induce Negative Group Velocity in marginally stable composites

Slesarenko, Galich, Li, Fang & Rudykh, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* (2018)

Domain Formation in Soft Particulate Composites

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